

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR AND LEADERSHIP

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada shaxsning tashkiliy xulq-atvori va yetakchilik qobiliyati har qanday biznes yoki tashkilot muvaffaqiyatida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynashi, shuningdek, korporativ muhitda inson xatti-harakatlari mahsuli va samarali yetakchiligi ijobiy o'zgarishlarga olib kelishi mumkinligi o'rganilib, tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: xulq-atvor, yetakchilik qobiliyati, xatti-harakat, korporativ muhit, iqtisodiy samaradorlik.

Abstract: The article analyzes that organizational behavior and leadership skills of a person play a decisive role in the success of any business or organization. It is also studied and analyzed that the product of human behavior and effective leadership can lead to positive changes in the corporate environment.

Key words: behavior, leadership ability, behavior, corporate environment, economic efficiency.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется, что организационное поведение и лидерские качества человека играют решающую роль в успехе любого дела или организации. Также изучается и анализируется, что продукт человеческого поведения и эффективного лидерства может привести к положительным изменениям в корпоративной среде.

Ключевые слова: поведение, лидерские способности, поведение, корпоративная среда, экономическая эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

Beginning with early 2021, the news bars of many authoritative business-related sources started dazzling with headlines describing 'Great Resignation', also named as 'Great Attrition', 'Turnover Tsunami', or 'Big Quit' (Bloomberg, 2022; Forbes – Cantalupo, G., 2022; HBR.org, 2022). The activity has been characterized as ongoing economic trend implying diverse employees massively leaving jobs; the feature to highlight is that vast majority of the resignations are undertaken voluntarily (Rosenberg and Rosenberg, 2022).

However, several authors had indicated abnormal fluctuations during 2002-2006, and highly abnormal indicators after Global Financial Crisis of 2007-2008 continuing later on (Coles and Mortensen, 2016; Cahuc, et al., 2016); whereas, most of the surrounding factors were considered to relate to the nature of crisis itself, its logical consequences and subsequent stabilization (Rose and Spiegel, 2012).

Recently, the Economic Policy Institute (EPI, 2022) presented a wide scale research providing the data analysis, namely JOLTS (Job Openings and Labor Turnover Survey) that seems to relatively support the references of pre-Big Quit period authors (Figures 1 and 2).

COMMUNICATION, AS THE TOOL FOR IDENTIFYING AND FORESEEING THE CAUSES

Soon after recognizing that Great Resignation is actually ongoing, many sources published the reports researching potential causes of resigning by employees (McKinsey, 2022; New Indian Express, 2022; The Economist, 2022). Extensive majority of them, being a reactive activity towards the occurrence, consists of survey replies communicated from present and ex-employees (Ibid). Recently, Gloat.com (2022) conducted its independent poll over 1000 employees and processed the replies; among all the emphasizes, the followings seem worth highlighting:

- 48.1% are or will be searching for new job within next 90 days;
- 54% of employees feel "their employer does not take their future interests and aspirations into account enough" (Ibid);

- 29.3% stated that their employer did not outline clear paths for their future development;
- All in all, resulting in 73.9% of highly qualified employees feel “there are better opportunities outside of their organization” (Ibid).

Figure 1: Total hires, layoffs, and quits (2000-2022)

Source: www.epi.org, 2022

Figure 2: The job-seekers ratio (2000-2021)

Source: www.epi.org, 2022

Most of the researches seem to conclude on the lack in awareness of employees needs and ambitions by their organizations and management. Cantalupo G (2021) from Forbes Communication Council provides a sample of ‘The Great Resignation Letter’, which grasped generalized causes of leaves, in its recommendations for sound retention policy and measures against Big Quit (Appendix I). Among all the five prioritized reasons, four of them directly (while №2 indirectly) imply on the tendency that ‘bosses do not listen to employees enough’ (Ibid). Fortune (2022), reviewing the report by US Bureau of Labor Logistics, highlighted the most impacted industries by the Great Resignation (Figure 3).

Taking into account that the top 7 industries are directly impacted by pandemic restrictions themselves, Fortune also notifies about considerable discrepancy in leaves proportions between blue-collar and white-collar workers (the latter is only 5%); to note, the first are the ones who are ordinarily affected by deficit of communication with superior due to their eased substitutability and number of workers (Mills, 2002).

Figure 3: Industries with highest percentages of workers quitting

Source: US BLS cited in Forbes, 2022

Simultaneously with many sources are improving communication policies and conducting reactive researches upon the causes of massive resignations, CNBC (2020) published an AI-based analysis with the list of “12 companies workers don’t want to leave”. One of the weighty advantages of these companies are effective communication processes, conflict resolution procedures and sound employee retention policies – the measures that had been integrated and practiced before the global pandemic and the Great Resignation trend (Ibid; Newsweek, 2022). The companies from the list such as, Delta, Cisco, Microsoft and Coca-Cola (and others) seem to have been facilitating successful communication framework throughout their performance period (Ibid). De Smet, et al., (2022) report that while companies develop advanced motivation schemes and set up favourable organization conditions for employees, they face difficulties in identifying their timely preferences and “do not fully understand why employees are leaving”; they also attach the diagram that represents diversification of job quits (Appendix II). As a result, organizations seem to apply their elaborated inspiration and support techniques for the assumed needs of employees without sufficient critical analysis of the actuality and correspondence of those needs with the employees themselves. Further, the authors call for transforming ‘the Great Attrition’ into ‘the Great Attraction’ directing the organizations to focus on maintenance of communication processes on permanent basis with the aim of enabling foreseeing and prevention of negative results (Ibid). CNBC (2020) supported this notion with its “top anti-resignation companies” list where the management does not seem to invent extraordinary solutions for employees’ retention but proactively maintain high level communication every day minimizing turnover “at all times”; cruciality of communication was also supported by a range of researches (Fortune, 2022; Global Impact, 2021; Maurer and Maurer, 2021).

Evaluation of HR structure, communication schemes, conflict resolution procedures and employees retention policies of several companies from the list above tends to present application of popular and widely accepted methods (Habib, 2016; Microsoft, 2022; Chen, 2016); nevertheless, frequent sessions on permanent basis considerably contribute to their overall corporate responsibility in regards to their primary stakeholders, i.e., employees. Within the further analysis, main bullet points among all the practices have been extracted and generalised.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Firstly, development of effective communication methods and channels is to be structured, or “the right person receives the right information in the right way at the right time” (ACCA, 2020). This general instruction is regarded not only for business communications, but for employees’ preferences and wishes, offers and demands, training and development, alongside with being open-minded for their ideas (Paschal, 2020).

Secondly, any cases of communication “distortion” and “noises” should be minimized (Ibid). The communication channel is to retain the initial message by an employee while being eventually delivered to the authorized superior that is competent to handle with it (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Case of communication

Source: ACCA Handbook – F1, 2020

Thirdly, elaboration of convenient and effective conflict resolution procedures – the model that is oriented on achieving ‘win-win’ results (Zhang, et al., 2018). Here, a sufficient place should be left for reaching satisfying compromised consensus for arguing parties, employees. Additionally, specially organized standing mediation and arbitration (for more serious occurrences) committees that are to resolve the conflict with impartiality and responsiveness (Ibid).

Fourthly, establishment of psychological support departments to deal with inner personal self-conflicts of employees. Psychological aid at workplace nowadays may be considered as an undeniable part in facilitating stable and favourable working conditions among staff members (Lee, 2021).

Finally, development of a sound informal communication strategy. Merely 10% out of the whole amount of communication inside an organization are performed formally while the informal one enjoys boundless freedom and provides more freedom of expression for employees. Undoubtedly, a huge proportion of those communication contents – being a ‘grapevine’ product – may be questioned for reliability and trust, however, the authors tend to insist on cultivation of impactable information communication pool and channels for superior managers vis-à-vis employees (Radovic Markovic and Salamzadeh, 2018).

Summarizing, once the arising needs and preferences of employees are identified they are to be applied with further mechanisms addressing those with appropriate organizational human resource tools further in the paper.

MOTIVATION THEORIES, TO ADDRESS THE IDENTIFIED VALUES AND NEEDS

As it was discussed, recent events around the world, such as, coronavirus, isolation, self-reassessment and changes in self-awareness, have changed not only people’s lifestyle and work, but also their underlying values and perceptions about life itself and career goals for future. During the pandemic situation, labor market changed its form and most people were induced to reconsider their path and make fundamental changes to their work as well.

The Great Resignation is one of the products of this inner personal reconsideration and values reassessment. This phenomenon means individuals around the world are leaving their job positions due to different reasons at very high rate; the reasons may be related to several factors, e.g., cultural identity, values, geographic location, type of job, financial and social conditions – yet these reassessments have been triggered by the pandemic (Chopra, 2022). Eventually this situation is leading to employers under pressure of seeking for new employees.

After pandemic situation when people were about to return their pre-pandemic life, this trend appeared and spread around the world. Especially in the US most companies have experienced this challenge. According to the research conducted by MIT Sloan (2021) around 24 million US citizens left their job position between April and September in 2021. Being more specific, the majority of this percentage was occupied more by low salary workers rather than high salary ones (blue-collar vs white-collar workers). Another research that has been conducted by Ion Cook (2021) and with his team within the sampling framework of more than 9 million employees’ records from more than 4,000 global companies revealed that these workers were mainly at mid-career level, i.e., middle-level employees.

High levels of resignations are more recorded in healthcare, hospitality and tech fields. Moreover, the dominant resigned age group is accounted to be in-between 30-40 aging period. Studies has showed that even world’s biggest companies like Space X Tesla, Goldman Sachs and Netflix have also been experiencing high attrition rates ever.

Drawing up a small conclusion out of the statistics extracts presented, it may be clearly seen that it is not only about salary dissatisfaction, it is more profound than it seems to be (Gloat, 2022). The research hereby leads us to the question: What are the real causes of these high resignations?

It is not a secret that Covid-19 imposed extensively high organizational and psychological stress, so changed working conditions totally. Almost each market suffered and had to transform in regards to the new realities imposed. However, that period granted individuals sufficient time and opportunity to add clarity to their relationship with their job, colleagues and work/life balance. People became more self-aware upon their own emotions, needs and values.

These are the words of one resigned person, Sara Adamski, extracted and highlighted in one of the reports: "The pandemic woke me up and I started questioning why I started doing that to myself" (Elting, 2021). She, being 26-year-old, used to work as a cook in a northern Alaska tourist destination. The research further provides a range of extracts of feasible replies and characterizations from respondents who make attempts to precisely explain that particular decision made (Ibid). Nevertheless, these reasons may not be considered as applicable for all related situations worldwide, in some cases people were reported to have left their jobs in search for better opportunities, for better growth chances and more flexibility. Several groups of respondents even totally have changed their job direction and nature after realizing that there is a very little chance for these sectors to recover after the world changes (EPI, 2022).

Research from MIT Sloan (2021) showed that another potential reason for such economic and social trend lays within the context of organizational culture. In toxic cultures where employees were not able to achieve recognition or other non-material rewards, such as appreciation and engagement, mainly left their positions. According to the research, "a toxic corporate culture is 10.4 times more powerful than compensation" – what probably induces many people to re-evaluate current life path and the ones that they had planned or dreamt about (Ibid).

Within the perspective of motivational component of HR and organizational behaviour, it may be described as a gap between employee's expectations in reality and employer's perception about what their employees seek. This issue is to be explained within the framework of two factor theory popularly labelled as Motivation-Hygiene theory. Meaning behind the theory implies the notion that the source from what individuals become satisfied are not the same with substance from which employees become dissatisfied. Therefore, if factors divided into two broad groups: satisfiers (motivators) and dissatisfiers (hygiene factors) may be classified. Most employers are noticed to be confusing importance and equality of both these factors. Hygiene factors are standardly salary work conditions and security. Focusing only on lacking hygiene factors is not capable to satisfy the whole load of demand for a sound employee retention. For this reason, researches report about unforeseen abnormal occurrences, such as resigning from job even while receiving relatively high waging. At this point, the majority managers failed to equate the pressure burdened by the pandemic factors vs the maintained employees retention policies at that time. Motivational factors like achievement, recognition, involvement and advancement seem to have dominated and be more of value for employees (Elting, 2021). The ideal condition might be recommended is to organize optimization of hygiene factors and maximization of motivation factors simultaneously. The emphasis here to be taken into account is that most resigning workers are at their mid-career level. Maslow's Hierarchy would also support the proposed suggestion since proves that most employees are mainly at the esteem and self-actualization point (stage within the hierarchy) – what may imply that they want more than financial benefit or means for conforming their minimal life needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Basing on findings some conclusions and recommendations can be made from motivation perspective:

Presence of Great Resignation in the US has been proved by several studies and statistical evidences. There are several reasons for this situation to develop which are related to individuals' emotional intelligence and motivational concepts. It requires today's CEO immediately react for the situation and accept feasible strategies, alongside with full reassessment of those in turn.

First of all, one standardized program can't be applied for all the organizations and cultures – people. Hence, tailored or customized approach should be used for every organization or country. However, there have been provided a list of milestone suggestions to be taken into account.

Managers have to look at their employees like a human but not resource (machine) that is designed for tasks execution without related emotional implications. Emotional Intelligence is to be further studied, understood and address workers' emotions, identifying their real values and needs (Fortune, 2022). To further develop the suggestion, it means monitoring and noticing employees' emotions in a proper way to provide timely and suitable encouragements with the aim of inducing them to perform better, behave calmer and stay longer.

Offering competitive pay and promotions is also one of the major components hereby. Salary is the first thing to attract workers, Simon and Enz (1995) and Wiley (1997) found that the best tools to motivate employees are the promotions and growth opportunities (cited in Curtis, et al., 2009). Yet, managers should not forget that priorities changed to the work/life balance side more than ever (Liu, 2020).

The next point is more flexibility and freedom for employees. Flexibility of working hours, form of work (distance/office) and geo-location transformed into substantially important components of job positions, especially after pandemic (Forbes, 2022).

Creating purpose for workers. In general, knowing that what an employee is doing the work that is meaningful and important motivates him/her more than other benefits and rewards.

Finally, more attention should be paid to working environment. Studies have proved that friendly and favorable organizational environment can assist as an incentive for employees in workplaces (Forbes, 2022).

PROFILE ANALYSIS, AS A MEANS OF PRODUCTIVITY INCREASE FOR THE APPLIED TOOLS

The study on Uzbekistan cases of the Great Resignation was made in International School of Finance Technology and Science LLC (ISFT Institute, hereafter – Institute) and the Ministry for the Development of Information Technology and Communication (hereafter – Ministry) (confirmations attached in the Appendices III and IV). The study indicates that during pandemic period of 2 years, the Institute had almost 50 percent turnover rate, with more than 47 employees of nearly 100 resigning, whereas the Ministry's central department having 142 employees had received resignation from 31 people (22 percent) during the pandemic situation.

The case studies show that among those who resigned 45 percent were aged from 24 to 32. However, the cases of resignation also included those who were aged up to 57.

Building personal profile of people resigning in Uzbekistan taking both cases might be stated as, people aged 24-32 years with 1-3 years' work experience at their work place – mainly men with 1 and more children, and with documental residing in distance or in regions outside Tashkent. Continuing building the profiles, it might be stated that they varied among the cases, yet with some features being similar; drawing conclusive correspondence in-between caused complications due to limited sampling size.

For the Institute case personnel, personality traits in general were observed to be extraverted, with strong conscientiousness, whereas, as for the Ministry's data indicates personnel being conscientious while lacking communication and are to be characterized as mostly as being introverted.

Evaluating the Great Resignation in USA, contradicting evidences were found Great Resignation, Cook I. (2021) indicated people inclined to quit their jobs are aged 30-45, whereas Caporal J. (2022) found them to be millennials. Probably this is related to geographical factoring of sampling location.

Constructing personality traits of people resigning in USA, it might be stated that they are 26-45 years old, both males and females, with five or more years of work experience. Further, being generally millennials, as stated above, Deal J. (2010), in understanding personality traits of them, indicates their inclination towards openness, diversity, team-orientation, being keen on flexibility and maintaining work-life balance.

Understanding personality traits of the employees by managers might help organization to attain more productivity with regard to better assignment of employees with traits and abilities (Wirght T., 2003). Moreover, Khedhaouria A. and Cucchic A. (2019), applying personality theories, found turnover rates might increase as any act of misconduct between employer and employees appears, including companies inner culture, norms, communication with managers, procedures and etc.

In addition, Kampkötter P. (2016) identified that managers might miss talents and crucial employees with misconduct on performance appraisal sessions. He also identified that given same conditions of employment job satisfaction rate varied substantially as measure for personality traits performance appraisals were conducted. Dipboye R. (2018) identified that using personality traits might influence management practices' effectiveness in retaining employees.

Moreover, Nadine N. and Abubakr S. (2019) examining personality traits in attaining talent found evidence on attracting employees with aligns with companies' values, thus preventing turnover rate at the time of employments processes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

About building recommendations to obtain and keep high retention rate of employees, the literature (Zhang and Gowan, 2012) states assigning employees with their personality traits using the 'Big Five' personality traits (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Costa & McCrae, 1995). In addition, Kampkötter P. (2016) stated that applying personality characteristics tool is adopted to impact the effectiveness of personnel choose, assigning, and keeping

high retention rates. Moreover, as Sarwar et.al. (2020) indicated that the Big Five personality traits, also being important in job appraisal, are crucial in understanding job turnover rate. In hypothesis analysis of OCEAN traits and intent to quit and turnover, they found relationship between turnover rate and conscientiousness being strong and moderate for relationship with extraversion, emotional stability (neuroticism) and agreeableness. Thus, supporting evidence of importance in assigning employees with their personality traits.

Additionally, with the development of IT technologies and Covid-19 consequences, companies might combine work schedules considering personality traits with appropriate work location (distance or on the side), increasing flexibility of employees. For instance, according to Global Talent Trends (2022), 51 percent of employees wish their firm provided greater flexibility at the workplace, leading to the conclusion that using combined approach might support positive retention rates, with regard to their traits being appropriately allocated.

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